

A QUASI-EXPERIMENTAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE EFFECTIVENESS OF INCENTIVE SPIROMETRY ON INSPIRATORY MUSCLE STRENGTH AMONG PATIENTS UNDERGOING CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFT SURGERY

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Abstract—: CABG is often indicated when coronary arteries have a 50 to 99 percent obstruction. The obstruction being bypassed is typically due to arteriosclerosis, atherosclerosis, or both. Arteriosclerosis is characterized by thickening, loss of elasticity, and calcification of the arterial wall, most often resulting in a generalized narrowing in the affected coronary artery. Post-operative cardiopulmonary health is severely compromised with impaired pulmonary and respiratory function mediated by such factors as chest wall pain, decreased respiratory function mediated by such factors as chest pain, decreased respiratory muscle strength, reduced exercise capacity and exercise tolerance, and anxiety with the resumption of more vigorous physical activity. Muscle strength can be essential for performance and might be altered in patient with ischemic heart disease.

Objectives :

- 1.To assess the effectiveness of incentive spirometry on inspiratory muscle strength among patients undergoing CABG.
- 2.To associate the inspiratory muscle strength with selected clinical variables.

Methodology : The study used quasi experimental design with 60 patients who underwent coronary artery bypass grafting were assigned in two groups experimental group (n=30) and control group (n=30) before and after the CABG the intervention were measurement. I advised the patient to do exercise on incentive spirometry which is planned for three sessions 8am,2pm and 9pm.I explained the procedure to the patient in detail. Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise and measuring the inspiratory muscle strength through chest expansion. Data was compared between pre- and post-intervention at baseline and the variation between the pre-post-test clinical variables, chest expansion. Day 1 on the day of admission, Day 2 after 4 hours of extubation whichever is later, day 6 post op on the day of discharge whichever is later. which were compared using the Chi-square test. Values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant

Conclusion .: The present study demonstrated that the addition of incentive spirometry, this randomized controlled trial resulted in a faster recovery of inspiratory muscle strength and chest expansion. It is also shown that incentive spirometry is a safe intervention in early postoperative period in CABG surgery

Keywords- Incentive spirometry, Muscle strength, CABG (Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery)

I. INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is expanding worldwide and according to world health organization (WHO) ,7.5 million people die every year from CVD, with 75% of these deaths occurring in low- and middle-income countries. Coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG).¹ decreased functional capacity and muscle strength are expected outcome in patients following coronary artery bypass graft CABG. Pulmonary complications such as atelectasis, pleural effusion, and pneumonia are also expected post-operative complication outcomes for these individuals' undergoing CABG for the treatment of patients with poor inspiratory muscle performance, with symptoms of dyspnea, low exercise tolerance, and low functional status.^{1,2}

Coronary artery bypass grafting remains the most widely used treatment modality for coronary artery disease, the procedure is associated with several cardiac and non-cardiac complication. Post -operative cardiopulmonary health is severely compromised with impaired pulmonary and respiratory function mediated by such factors such as chest wall pain, decreased respiratory function mediated, reduced exercise capacity, exercise tolerance and anxiety with the resumption of more vigorous physical activity.³ Muscle strength can be essential for the performance and it might be altered in patient with ischemic heart disease.⁴

Coronary artery bypass grafting is associated with reduced ventilatory muscle strength and consequent worsening of functional capacity. Inspiratory muscle is a tool to reduce the deleterious effects caused by cardiac surgery. By imposing a resistance in the inspiratory phase, it restores the integrity of the inspiratory muscle and also preventing hypotrophy and fatigue through pressure linear load devices.⁵

Incentive spirometry (IS) It is the most frequently used tool; it is a handled device used postoperative to reach effective inspiration. Patients practicing IS (Incentive spirometry) provide visual and positive feedback after inhaling at a determined flow volume rate and holding the inflation for at least 3sec IS (Incentive spirometry) intended to mimic normal sighing or yawning but supporting the patient to take long and slow deep breaths. This reduces pleural tension, supporting enhanced lung expansibility and improving ventilation-perfusion. In addition, atelectasis may be prevented or reversed when the procedure is repeated regularly.⁶

Incentive spirometry was developed to reduce atelectasis and in widespread clinical use. However, without (IS) Incentive spirometry use adherence data, the effectiveness of IS cannot be determined.⁷ The oscillation of the air flow is generated by breaking and repairing the magnetic gravity through the plug where the air passing through the unit is interrupted periodically, which is routinely utilize after a cardiac procedure. Incentive spirometry is intended to encourage the patient to take a full breath, impersonating unconstrained yawning or moaning, expanding or keeping up breathed-in lung volume, and enhancing sputum expectoration.⁽⁸⁾ To

prevent the incidence of most postoperative complication, some of the interventions are to prevent the pulmonary complication after CABG, which can be highlighted by deep breathing exercise and Incentive Spirometry (IS). Continuous positive airway pressure and early mobilization we can use some methods for the importance in the pulmonary function. Incentive Spirometry (IS) is used for improvement in exchange of gases and oxygen, depending on the cooperation of patient. It is most widely used especially in management of patient in postoperative period of cardiac surgery, but the results supporting the use of such equipment to reduce postoperative pulmonary complication which leads to controversies in the improvement of pulmonary function in the exchange of gases and oxygenation after coronary artery bypass surgery.⁹

Almost 400,000 CABG surgeries are performed every year. It is the most commonly performed major surgical procedure, but surgical trends have decreased as the use of alternative options such as medical treatment and Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) have increased. Long-term survival, major adverse cardiovascular events, and factors associated with elevated risk in all adults ≤ 50 years of age that underwent CABG young adults had lower long-term mortality and incidence of adverse cardiovascular events than older patients after CABG. The incidences of pneumonia and ARF (Acute respiratory failure) after CABG are higher and the most common comorbidity is hypertension in patients undergoing CABG.³⁹

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

“A Quasi-experimental Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Incentive Spirometry on Inspiratory Muscle Strength among Patients undergoing Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery”.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the effectiveness of incentive spirometry on inspiratory muscle strength among patients undergoing CABG.
2. To associate the inspiratory muscle strength with the selected clinical variables

IV. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

1. Effectiveness:

- Dictionary: The degree to which something is successful in producing a desired result; success.
- Operational: In this study the capability of producing the desired result.

2. Incentive spirometer:

- Dictionary: An incentive spirometry is a hand-held medical device used to help patients improve the functioning of the lungs. By training patients to take slow deep breaths, this simplified spirometer facilitates lung expansion and strengthening.
- Operational: In my study an incentive spirometry is a device that measures the volume of the air inhaled into the lungs during inspiration.

3. Inspiratory muscle strength:

- Dictionary: Inspiratory muscle strength is a technique that aims to improve the function of the respiratory muscle through specific exercise.
- Operational: In the study, an inspiratory muscle strength is the resistance that focuses on strengthening the muscle that helps one breath. When these muscles are routinely trained for a few weeks, they adapt, become strong and can perform the activities. **Coronary artery bypass graft (CABG)**
- Dictionary: A coronary artery bypass graft (CABG) is a surgical procedure used to treat coronary heart disease. It diverts blood around narrowed or clogged parts of the major arteries to improve blood flow and oxygen supply to the heart.
- Operational: Coronary artery bypass surgery creates a new path for blood to flow around a blocked or partially blocked artery in the heart.

V. HYPOTHESIS

1. H_0 : There will be no significant effect of incentive spirometry on inspiratory muscle strength at 0.05 level of significance.

2. H_1 : There will be significant effect of incentive spirometry on inspiratory muscle strength at 0.05 level of significance

VI. ASSUMPTION

Patients are at risk of reducing their muscle strength after CABG

VII. ETHICAL ASPECTS

1. Ethical clearance from institution ethics committee

- a. The study proposal was approved by the institutional ethics committee of the college.
- b. Permission was taken from concerned authorities of selected hospital
- c. Information about the study was given to the participants

- d. Informed written consent was taken from all the terms of agreement.
- e. Confidentiality of the data was ensured
- f. Information was not released outside the terms of agreement
- g. Subjects was protected from all types of harm.

VIII. RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design:- Quasi experimental study research design

The quasi-experimental design was used due to lack of randomization of sample to the control and experimental group less same size and presence of extraneous variables which affect the study. Non randomized control group design was used.

Non -randomized control group pre-test and post- test design

Fig 1.2 Non-randomized control group pre-test - post-test design

SETTING OF THE STUDY

The study will be conducted in selected hospital in Pune city.

A. Inclusion criteria

1. Patients undergoing elective/planned CABG surgery.
2. Age > 18 years

B. Exclusion Criteria

1. Emergency CABG patient
2. Critically ill patients.
3. Patients who are not willing to participate in study.

.Process of Data Collection

- Patient undergoing CABG surgery.
- Scrutinized the patient from inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- Enrolled alternate patient in control and experimental group.
- Explained the study purpose and taken the informed consent from the patient.
- Administered the pre-test to samples in English language.
- Researcher revises the advice given by physician and motivates the participants to follow them.
- **Post-test:** Post test was taken after the patient is extubated and before the patient is discharged

C. Description of The Tool

1. *Section A:* Section A:- Clinical variables Age ,Gender -Male ,Female: History of pulmonary disease,History of smoking (Yes / No)
2. Parameters to Check on Day 1pre op on the day of admission,Day 2after 4 hr of extubation,Day 6-on the day of discharge

Section B: Steps for use of Incentive Spirometry with flow Incentive Spirometer

1	Place patient in a high fowler’s position.
2	Take a pillow to support incision site to keep the muscle moving as much while using spirometer. (If post operatively)
3	Instruct patient to breath out and breath in fully through mouth for few seconds.
4	Instruct patient to put the mouthpiece in mouth and between the lips tightly around mouth piece. Make sure patient do not block the mouthpiece with tongue.
5	Instruct the patient to breath in slowly through mouth as deeply as he can.
4	Explain the patient to hold inspiration as long as possible
5	Ask the patient to remove the mouthpiece and exhale.
6	Exhale normally, then rest. Cough to clear your airway of mucus if needed.

D. Method Of Data Collection:

A. Permission from concerned authorities:-

- Prior to the collection of data, permission was obtained from the director academics of the selected hospital and consultants of the medicine.
- The purpose and nature of the study were explained to gain co-operation

.The data for main study was collected from 10/04/22 to 20/05/22. The data collection was done under the standard and laid down condition.

Process Of Data Collection :

Table: 3.4 Procedure of data collection.

Days	Day 1 (Pre op) On the day of admission	After 4hr of extubation Post op (Day 1)	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5	Day 6 Post op On the day of discharge whichever is later
Procedure	Deep breathing exercise (5- 10 mins daily) and Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive Spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise.	Incentive spirometry 3 times in a day 10 repetitions of inhalation and exhalation exercise
Time		9am	9 am	9 am	9 am	9 am	9 am
		2pm	2 pm	2 pm	2 pm	2 pm	2 pm
		8pm	8 pm	8 pm	8 pm	8 pm	8 pm
Baseline parameter		Day 1 (Pre op) On the day of admission	Day 2 / After 4hr of Extubation Post op (Day 1) whichever is later		Day 6 Post op/ On the day of discharge whichever is later		
FVC(Lit) Forced vital capacity		9am					
		2pm					
		8pm					
Chest expansion (In inches)	Time	Insp	exp	Insp	exp	Insp	exp
	9am						

E. Plan Of Data Analysis

The analysis was done on the base of objectives to be tested. The collected data had been organized, tabulated, and analysed by using descriptive form

IX. RESULT

Section I: -

Table 4.1: Descriptions of the sample according to clinical variables in experimental group and control group

Parameters		Experiment		Control	
		f	%	F	%
Age	Up to 50	6	20	11	36.66
	51 – 60	7	23.33	7	23.33
	61 – 70	9	30	5	16.66
	71 & above	8	26.66	7	23.33
Gender	Male	18	60	15	50
	Female	12	40	15	50
H/O of Pulmonary disease	Yes	3	10	1	3.33
	No	27	90	29	96.66
H/O of smoking	Yes	1	3.33	0	0
	No	29	96.66	30	100

Age:

Majority of 9 (30%) patients were in the age group of (61-70) followed by 8 (26.66%) subjects in the age group of 71 and above. 7 (23.33%) were in the age of 61-70, 6(20%) were in the age group of up to and the total patients included in the experimental group were 30. While in control group up to 50 are group were 11(36.66), 7 (23.33) patients under the age of 51 – 60 ,7(23.33%) 71 and above ,5 (16.66%) under the age group of 61-70 and the total patients in control group were 30. Using Chi-square = 2.68, P = 0.44

Gender: In experimental group 18(60%) Male and 12(40%) Female, and 15(50%) Male and 15(50%) Female in control group.

History of pulmonary disease: Table shows that there are 3(10%) subjects from experimental group had the history of pulmonary disease, and 27(90%) subjects are not having pulmonary disease. Where in 1(3.33%) subject from control group had the history of pulmonary disease and 29(96.66%) subjects are not having the history of pulmonary disease.

Fisher exact test: P = 0.61

History of smoking: 1(3.33%) Subjects from experimental group had a history of smoking and 29(96.66%) subjects are not having the history of smoking.30(100%) from the control group were nonsmokers. Fisher exact test: P = 1

Graph no 1: Bar diagram showing the Age wise distribution of cases in experiment and control group

Graph no 1: Bar diagram showing the Age wise distribution of cases in experiment and control group

Graph no 2: Bar diagram showing Gender wise distribution of cases in experiment and control group

Graph no 3: Bar diagram showing the H/O pulmonary disease wise distribution of cases in experiment and control group

Graph no 4: Bar diagram showing the H/O smoking wise distribution of cases in experiment and control group

Section II: - Comparison of pre and post-test FVC among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

FVC	Experiment (n=30)		Control (n=30)		Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Pre op. (Day 1)	870.00	164.317	930.00	120.773	1.61	0.11
Post op. (Day 2)	640.00	103.724	640.00	103.724	0	1
Post op. (Day 6)	830.00	129.055	660.00	122.051	5.24	<0.0001

Table 4.2 shows that there is no significant difference of pre op FVC day 1 and post of day2 between experimental group and control group as $P > 0.05$.

There is significant difference of post op day 6 between experimental and control group as $P < 0.0001$ i.e. FVC on post op day 6 was significantly more in the experimental group than control group.

Graph no 5: The bar diagram shows the comparison of pre and post-test FVC among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

Table 4.3: Comparison of FVC among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group.

Parameter	FVC (Lit)		t Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	870.00	164.317	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	640.00	103.724	4.80	<0.0001	26.44
Post op. (Day 6)	830.00	129.055	2	0.046	4.60
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			4.36	<0.0001	29.69

Table 4.3 shows that there is significant difference of FVC between pre-op day1 and post-op day2, day6 and between post of day2 and post op day6 in experiment group as $P < 0.0001$ and $P < 0.05$ i.e. FVC was significantly reduced after post op day2 (26.44%) and day6 (4.60%) and significantly increased from post of day2 to day 6 (29.69%).

Graph no 6: The bar diagram shows the Comparison of FVC among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group

Table 4.4: Comparison of FVC among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group

Parameter	FVC (Lit)		t Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	930.00	120.773	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	640.00	103.724	5.39	<0.0001	31.18
Post op. (Day 6)	660.00	122.051	5.20	<0.0001	29.03
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			1.41	0.16	3.13

Graph no7: The bar diagram shows the Comparison of FVC among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group

SECTION III: Comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

Table 4.5: Comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group.

Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)	Experiment (n=30)		Control (n=30)		Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Pre op. (Day 1)	39.63	2.834	39.80	2.797	0.23	0.82
Post op. (Day 2)	38.93	2.876	39.10	2.905	0.22	0.82
Post op. (Day 6)	39.63	2.834	39.10	2.905	0.72	0.48

Table 4.5 shows that there is no significant difference of chest expansion inspiration on pre-op. Day1, post op day2, post op day6 among patients undergoing CABG in experimental and control group as $P > 0.05$.

Graph no 8: The bar diagram shows comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group.

Table 4.6 Comparison of chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group.

(E=30)

Parameter	Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)		t Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	39.63	2.834	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	38.93	2.876	4.58	<0.0001	1.77
Post op. (Day 6)	39.63	2.834	0	1	0
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			4.58	<0.0001	1.80

Graph No 9: The bar graph shows the comparison of chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group

Table 4.7: Comparison of chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group.

(C=30)

Parameter	Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)		Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	39.80	2.797	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	39.10	2.905	4.58	<0.0001	1.76
Post op. (Day 6)	39.10	2.905	4.58	<0.0001	1.76
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			0	1	

Graph no 10: The bar graph diagram shows the comparison of chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group

SECTION IV: Comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group.

Table 4.8: Comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)	Experiment (n=30)		Control (n=30)		Z Value	P Value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Pre op. (Day 1)	40.63	2.834	40.80	2.797	0.23	0.82
Post op. (Day 2)	39.93	2.876	40.10	2.905	0.22	0.82
Post op. (Day 6)	40.63	2.834	40.10	2.905	0.72	0.48

Graph No 11: The bar diagram shows the comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

Table 4.9: Comparison of chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group

Parameter	Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)		Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	39.63	2.834	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	38.93	2.876	4.58	<0.0001	1.72
Post op. (Day 6)	39.63	2.834	0	1	0
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			4.58	<0.0001	1.75

Graph no 12: The bar diagram shows the comparison of chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in experiment group.

Table 4.10: Comparison of chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group

Parameter	Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)		Z Value	P Value	% change
	Mean	SD			
Pre op. (Day 1)	39.80	2.797	-	-	-
Post op. (Day 2)	39.10	2.905	4.58	<0.0001	1.72
Post op. (Day 6)	39.10	2.905	4.58	<0.0001	1.72
Post op. (Day 2) Vs Post op. (Day 6)			0	1	0

Graph no 13: The graph shows the comparison of chest expansion expiration among patients undergoing CABG between pre and post-test in control group.

SECTION V: Association of pre op and post op chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group and control group.

Table 4.11: Association of pre op (day1) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Pre op (day1) FVC	n	Pre op Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)		F Value	P Value
		Mean	SD		
600	6	38.33	3.386	0.81	0.46
900	21	39.90	2.700		
1200	3	40.33	2.887		

Graph no 14: The bar diagram shows the association of pre op (day1) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Table 4.12: Association of post op (day2) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Post op (day2) FVC	Post of Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)			t Value	P Value
	n	Mean	SD		
600	26	38.85	2.976	0.42	0.68
900	4	39.50	2.380		

TABLE II

Graph no 15: the bar diagram shows the association of post op (day2) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Table 4.13: Association of post op (day6) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Post op (day6) FVC	n	Post of Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)		t Value	P Value
		Mean	SD		
600	7	38.57	3.155	1.14	0.27
900	23	39.96	2.722		

Graph no 16: The graph bar shows the association of post-op (day6) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in experiment group

Table 4.14: Association of pre-op (day1) chest expansion inspiration and FVC in control group

Pre op (day1) FVC	n	Pre op Chest expansion Insp. (Inches)		t Value	P Value
		Mean	SD		
600 & 900	26	39.35	2.682	2.46	0.021
1200	4	42.75	1.500		

Graph no 21: the bar diagram shows that there is association of post-op (day2) chest expansion expiration and FVC in experiment group

Table 4.19: Association of post-op (day6) chest expansion expiration and FVC in experiment group

Post op (day6) FVC	Post of Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)			t Value	P Value
	n	Mean	SD		
600	7	39.57	3.155	1.14	0.27
900	23	40.96	2.722		

Graph no 22 : Association of post-op (day6) chest expansion expiration and FVC in experiment group

Table 4.20: Association of pre-op (day1) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

Pre op (day1) FVC	Pre of Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)			t Value	P Value
	n	Mean	SD		
600 & 900	26	40.35	2.682	2.46	0.021
1200	4	43.75	1.500		

Graph no 23: The bar diagram shows that there is association of pre-op (day1) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

Table 4.21: Association of post-op (day2) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

Post op (day2) FVC	Post op Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)			t Value	P Value
	n	Mean	SD		
600	26	39.69	2.867	2.07	0.048
900	4	42.75	1.500		

Graph no 24: The bar diagram shows that there is association of post-op (day2) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

Table 4.22: Association of post-op (day6) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

Post op (day6) FVC	Post op Chest expansion Exp. (Inches)			t Value	P Value
	n	Mean	SD		
600	24	39.88	2.724	0.84	0.41
900	6	41.00	3.688		

Graph no 25: The bar diagram shows that there is association of post-op (day6) chest expansion expiration and FVC in control group

X. DISCUSSION

Results discussed according to objectives and hypothesis in the light of other studies done in the area of Effectiveness of Incentive Spirometry on Inspiratory Muscle Strength Among Patients undergoing Coronary Artery Bypass Graft Surgery”.

A) *Finding related to descriptions of the sample according to clinical variables in experimental group and control group.*

The present study result revealed that, there is no significant difference in age, gender, history of pulmonary disease and history of smoking $P = 0.44$ There is the similarity between the findings of the study Sema Savci et.al. 2011 short-term effects of inspiratory muscle training in coronary artery bypass graft surgery. Their study shows that the clinical variables age, gender, history of smoking, show the significance significantly longer in the control group than the intervention group ($p < 0.05$).⁽¹⁸⁾

A prospective randomized controlled trial study conducted on preoperative incentive spirometry for preventing postoperative pulmonary complications in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass graft surgery by Essa M. Sweity et.al. 2021. The study findings showed there is no significant difference between the incentive spirometry and control groups in the incidence of postoperative atelectasis.⁽⁶⁾

A prospective cohort study is conducted on muscle strength trajectories and their association with postoperative health-related quality of life in patients undergoing coronary artery bypass grafting surgery by Johanneke Hartog et.al. 2023. The study finding shows that the history of pulmonary disease, showed a

considerable and significant decrease of 13% after surgery (from 6.1 to 5.3 N/kg, P -value < 0.001 , $F(1.6, 19.0) = 98.2$). Subsequently, the values rose to a significantly higher level compared to preoperatively (from 6.1 to 6.8 N/kg, P -value < 0.001 , $F(1.6, 19.0) = 98.2$)⁽²²⁾

B) Finding related to comparison of pre and post-test FVC among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

In present study shows that there is no significant difference of pre-op FVC day 1 and post-op of day2 between experimental group and control group as $P > 0.05$. There is significant difference of post-op day 6 between experimental and control group as $P < 0.0001$ i.e., FVC on post-op day 6 was significantly more in the experimental group than control group

A study conducted on Effectiveness of a perioperative pulmonary rehabilitation program following coronary artery bypass graft surgery by Jui-O Chen et.al. 2018 In the COPD group, FVC (0.85 L vs 1.25 L, $P < 0.01$), FEV₁ (0.75 L vs 1.08 L, $P < 0.01$), peak flow (0.99 L vs 1.79 L, $P < 0.01$) and FEF (0.68 L vs 1.15 L, $P < 0.01$) were significantly higher on postoperative day 14 compared to postoperative day 1. FVC (1.11 L vs 1.36 L, $P < 0.05$), FEV₁ (96 L vs 1.09 L, $P < 0.05$) and FEF (1.03 L vs 1.26 L, $P < 0.05$) were also significantly improved in the non-COPD group.²⁹

The meta-analysis conducted by Hadel Shahood Jul et.al. 2022. This study showed that there was no significant difference between the interventional and control groups in the pulmonary functions, including FEV1%, FVC% and Pi-max, favouring the interventional group. However, only the FEV1% showed homogenous results.⁽³⁰⁾

C) Finding related to comparison of pre and post-test chest expansion inspiration among patients undergoing CABG in experiment and control group

There is no significant difference of chest expansion inspiration on pre-op. day1, post-op day2, post-op day6 among patients undergoing CABG in experimental and control group as $P > 0.05$. There is the significant difference between of chest expansion inspiration between pre-op day1 & post-op day2, not significant on post-op of day6 and significant between post-op day2 and post-op day 6 in experimental group as $P < 0.0001$, $P = 1$ i.e., chest expansion inspiration was significantly reduced after post-op day2 (1.77%) and same on day6 and significantly increased from post-op of day2 to day 6 (1.80%).

A randomized clinical trial conducted a study on moderate to high intensity inspiratory muscle training improves the effect of combined training on exercise capacity in patients after CABG by Gaudino M et.al.

2015. The IMT + CT group showed significantly greater improvements in peak oxygen uptake ($1.3 \text{ mL} \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$; 95% confidence interval [95% CI], 0.5 to 2.2), distance covered during the 6MWT (78.8 m; 95% CI, 28.1 to 129.5), maximal inspiratory pressure (23.0 cmH_2O ; 95% CI, 9.3 to 36.7), IMT + CT group as a result of the intervention. ⁽³¹⁾

D) LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- A) The data was collected only through the clinical variables and two parameters.
- B) This study was limited to the hospitals of Pune city.
- C) The study was limited to the post-operative CABG patients.
- D) Data collection period was limited.

E) RECOMMENDATION

- A) A similar study may be replicated on large samples; thereby findings can be generalized.
- B) The study may be undertaken in different settings and different generalization of findings.
- C) A comparative study can be done by using other methods and to find the accuracy

D) CONCLUSION

The Present Study Demonstrated that the addition of incentive spirometry this randomized controlled trial resulted in a faster recovery of inspiratory muscle strength & chest expansion. It is also shown that incentive Spirometry is a safe intervention in early postoperative period in CABG surgery.

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